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The Effect of Human Relations and Communication Lesson on Eloquent Speaking Skill

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Abstract

In this study, the effect of human relations and communication lessons on eloquent speaking skills was examined by using the pretest-posttest control group model. 96 students studying at Hatay Mustafa Kemal University School of Physical Education and Sports participated in the research voluntarily in the spring semester of 2020-2021. The data were collected during the oral presentations made in the human relations and communication lesson with the Rating Scale to Assess Speaking Skills for Turkish Native Speakers developed by Bozkurt and Arica-Akkök (2019). Descriptive statistics were used to determine the level of speaking skills of physical education teacher candidates before and after speaking practices, and their standard deviation and arithmetic mean scores were examined. Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks Test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference in speaking skill scores before and after the lesson. According to the research findings; while the pretest averages of the experimental group students were lower than the control group, their posttest averages were higher than the control group. It was determined that there was a significant difference between the scores of the students participating in the study before and after the experiment from the speaking skills observation form, and when the mean rank and totals of the difference scores were taken into account, it was seen that this difference was in favor of the positive ranks, that is, the posttest score. It was determined that there was no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores obtained from the speaking skills observation form of the students participating in the study in the control group.

Keywords: Human Relations, Communication, Eloquent Speaking, Effective Communication, Listening

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduce the Problem

People in the world are divided into two in terms of the act of speaking in every environment of their individual and social relations; speaking and listening. We express our thoughts and feelings with speech, which is the shortest and most striking way. The place of speaking, especially correct, effective and nice speaking, is very valuable in our business, social and private lives. In this process, the one who speaks well influences the listener with what she/he says (Şahzade, 2007).

Man is in communication by nature; therefore they feel the need to explain, understand, learn and interpret. This need, which we call communication, is as important as food, drink, sleep and shelter. For this reason, communication is a necessity for human beings and is a dynamic process that started with the history of humanity (Özdemir, 2017). The main purpose of communication is to survive. We communicate in order to establish relationships, to get to know people, to introduce ourselves, to obtain information, in general, to meet our personal and social needs (Erdoğan, 2011). The sounds we hear, a shape we see, an image or writing, a movement, a touch must have a common meaning. Today, letters, numbers, words, signs, graphics, images and body language elements are used in the coding system. A large part of our life; speaking, listening, reading, writing, watching, in a more general sense, is through communication. Diversifying and accelerating such an important need, finding new symbols has been one of the primary goals of people and has constantly developed communication tools by using technology. Especially with the introduction of the internet and mobile communication tools into our lives, it has become much easier to communicate more quickly with larger audiences. It is possible to classify the communication tools we use today depending on the form of communication, the nature of the message and its purpose: Natural means of communication, artificial means of communication; Personal and mass media; Written, verbal and non-verbal communication tools; such as technological and artistic communication tools (Özdemir, 2017).

The concepts of listening and hearing are often confused with each other. Hearing is the sending of sound waves perceived by the ear to the brain via nerves. Listening is a cognitive process that includes hearing (Güneş, 2007). Students who understand what they read and listen to, who have advanced analysis and synthesis skills, who can express their feelings and thoughts effectively, who have high academic success, also have high listening skills (Aktaş ve Gündüz, 2004). When something is told, it is expected to be listened to (Henderson, 2008).

From time to time, we complain about the people we communicate with because they do not understand us. At this point, you should also consider: Don't they understand us? Or do we not explain ourselves well? An effective body language means an effective expression of our feelings and thoughts. Using body language well contributes to our understanding of the body language of others. The effect of non-verbal elements in the transmission of a message is 60-65% (Navarro, 2016). Effective and eloquent speaking is speech that provides interaction between the listener and the speaker, attracts the attention and interest of the listeners, thus stimulating them in line with an active behavior; knowing what, when, where, how to say (Harkins, 2005).

It is essential for today's people to have a good expression skills. The individual's adaptation to his/her cultural environment, being successful in his/her profession, developing a solid personality; It depends on expressing his thoughts and feelings to those around him effectively and accurately. A successful speaking is a well-planned speech. The speech plan consists of the purpose of the speech, the subject of the speech and the main lines. Introduction section; It should include the purpose of the speech, a complete summary of what will be said, and then move on to the explanation section. In the conclusion part, which is the most important part of the speech; a judgment is made on the basis of what is told during the speech. The examples that the speaker will use will not only support her/his thesis but will also be useful in attracting the attention of the audience. The examples given should be taken from real life. Examples from real life always attract the attention of the audience. During the conversation, attention should be paid to: Need, language rules, avoiding waste of words, benefiting from auditory and visual effects, not being memorized, being moderate in speaking time, accuracy and sincerity, liveliness and naturalness, volume-speed-tone of voice, eye contact, smiling, feeling of confidence in speaking, being respectful and tolerant, ensuring the participation of the audience (Şahin, 2007).

Regardless of the level of education, it is an unforgivable mistake for people to use their language incorrectly. Being able to express oneself accurately, effectively and completely is the most important point of education and development. In modern education systems, detailed studies should be carried out in order to use the language carefully and correctly. From this point of view, the aim of this study is to examine the effect of human relations and communication lessons on eloquent speaking skills.

2. Method

2.1 Model of the Research

In the research designed with the quantitative research method, the experimental model with a pre-test and post-test control group was used. In this model, there are two groups formed by unbiased assignment. Measurements are made before and after the experiment in both groups (Karasar, 2014).

Table 1: Symbolic view of the model

G ₁	R	O _{1.1}	X	O _{1.2}
G ₂	R	O _{2.1}		O _{2.2}

G: Group, R: Randomness, X: Independent variable, O: Observation

2.2 Study Group

96 students studying at Hatay Mustafa Kemal University School of Physical Education and Sports participated in the research voluntarily in the spring semester of 2020-2021. Ethics committee report dated 01.09.2021 and decision numbered 2021/8/10 was obtained from Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Social and Human Sciences Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage results of experimental and control groups according to gender variable

Group	Gender	n	%
Experimental Group	Female	20	41.7
	Male	28	58.3
	Total	48	100.0
Control Group	Female	18	37.5
	Male	30	62.5
	Total	48	100.0

According to Table 2, 41.7% of the experimental group participants were female and 58.3% male. On the other hand, 37.5% of the control group was female and 62.5% was male.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

Data were collected with the Speaking Skill Rating Scale for Native Turkish Speakers developed by Bozkurt and Arıca-Akkök (2019). Permission was obtained for the use of the scale. The scale is designed as a tool to provide feedback to the speaker in areas of strengths and weaknesses as part of the process evaluation. It consists of 30 items and sections on pronunciation, fluency, content-language use, and interaction-presentation strategies. The whole of the observation form or each part of it for the purpose can be used separately. The content validity value of all items in the observation form is over .80.

2.4 Data Collection Process

The data of the research were collected during the oral presentations made in the human relations and communication lesson in the spring semester of 2020-2021. As a result of the pre-test, the participants were divided into two as experimental and control groups. The eloquent skills of the experimental group were weaker than the control group. As a result of the experimental activity, it was aimed for the experimental group to reach or exceed the level of the control group. While training on eloquent skills was given to the experimental group in the human relations and communication lesson, no study was conducted in the control group. Human relations and communication lesson is a theoretical lesson for 2 hours per week. Pre-test presentations were made online on any topic determined by the students for 10 minutes, and during these presentations, the researcher filled in the observation form. Pre-test presentations were completed in 2 weeks, then speaking skills activities in the human relations and communication lesson were applied. Eloquent speaking activities were held for 10 weeks

within the framework of the curriculum topics of the human relations and communication lesson. At the end of ten weeks, the students were asked to make an online presentation for 10 minutes on a topic determined by the students, and the speaking skills observation form was filled again by the researcher during the presentation. Limitation of this research; Internet connection problems during online presentations.

2.5 Data Analysis

In order to determine the level of speaking skills of physical education teacher candidates before and after speaking practices, descriptive statistics were used and standard deviation and arithmetic mean scores were examined. Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks Test was applied to determine whether there was a significant difference in speaking skill scores before and after the lesson. The data were analyzed with the SPSS 22.0 computer program.

3. Results

Table 3: Descriptive statistical analysis results according to age and scale scores of the experimental and control groups

Group		Min.	Max.	X	Ss
Experimental Group	Age	19	30	22.89	2.92
	Pre-test Total	30	77	53.25	11.82
	Post-test Total	90	120	102.50	14.94
Control Group	Age	19	29	22.97	3.18
	Pre-test Total	30	120	91.25	21.42
	Post-test Total	63	117	93.12	13.54

Table 3 shows the descriptive statistical analysis results according to the age and scale scores of the experimental and control groups. While the pre-test averages of the experimental group students were lower than the control group, the post-test averages were higher than the control group. According to this, it is seen that the targeted level in the speaking skills practices applied in the human relations and communication lesson has been achieved.

Table 4: Wilcoxon signed-ranks test results for the pre and post-test scores of the experimental group on eloquent speaking skills

Post test- Pre test	n	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank	z	p
Negative Ranks	0	.00	.00	6.03*	.000
Positive Ranks	48	24.50	1176.00		
Ties	0				

* Based on negative ranks

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test results regarding whether the speaking skills of the participants before and after the experiment showed a significant difference are given in Table 4. The results of the analysis show that there is a significant difference between the pre-experiment and post-experiment scores of the students participating in the study from the speaking skills observation form, $z=6.03$, $p<.01$. When the mean rank and totals of the difference scores are taken into account, it is seen that this difference is in favor of the positive ranks, that is, the post-test score. According to these results, it can be said that the education is given in the human relations and communication lesson has an important effect on the development of students' speaking skills.

Table 5: Wilcoxon signed-ranks test results for the pre and post-test scores of the control group on eloquent speaking skills

Post test- Pre test	n	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank	z	p
Negative Ranks	28	19.73	552.50	.112*	.903
Positive Ranks	19	30.29	575.50		
Ties	1				

* Based on negative ranks

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test results regarding whether the speaking skills of the control group show a significant difference are given in Table 5. The results of the analysis show that there is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the students participating in the study from the speaking skills observation form, $z=.112$, $p>.01$. According to these results, it can be said that there is no improvement in the speaking skills of the students who did not attend the human relations and communication lesson.

4. Discussion

In this study, in which the effect of human relations and communication courses on eloquence skills was examined; while the pre-test averages of the experimental group students were lower than the control group, the post-test averages were higher than the control group. According to this, it is seen that the targeted level in the speaking skills practices applied in the human relations and communication lesson has been achieved. It was determined that there was a significant difference between the pre-experiment and post-experiment scores of the students participating in the study from the speaking skills observation form. According to these results, it can be said that the education given in the human relations and communication lesson has an important effect on the development of students' eloquent skills. It was determined that there was no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores obtained from the speaking skills observation form of the students participating in the study in the control group. According to these results, it can be said that there is no improvement in the speaking skills of the students who did not attend the human relations and communication lesson.

When the studies in the literature are examined; Alan (2021) revealed that pre-service teachers' speaking self-efficacy perceptions are above the medium level, the gender variable is not a determining factor in speaking self-efficacy perceptions, and the grade level and department variables affect their speaking self-efficacy perceptions. Özdemir (2018) stated that pre-service teachers' speaking anxiety was moderate in the pre-test and low in the post-test; stated that making prepared speeches makes a significant difference in eliminating the speaking anxiety of pre-service teachers. Temiz (2015) stated that pre-service teachers who took pedagogical formation had very little speaking anxiety and that the speaking anxiety of pre-service teachers did not differ according to the variables of Turkish, Mathematics, Science and Music. Cengiz and Karabulut (2015) determined that education at the university affects the speaking skill positively, but according to the perceptions of female students, the instructors are insufficient in the development of this skill.

In the research of Sönmez (2014), it was stated that the correct and effective speaking skills could be taught to the students with the individual voice training course, but the studies could not be fully realized due to the inadequacy of the course hours; It has been revealed that the teacher should be a good role-model in teaching correct, beautiful and effective skills. Akkaya (2013) determined that pre-service teachers have psychological problems (not being able to speak in public, not speaking in one-to-one relationships), voice, tone emphasis, pronunciation mistakes, speech pause, lack of knowledge, inability to apply grammar rules, inability to focus on speaking, and speech problems arising from social obstacles due to physical reasons. Eyüp (2013)'s study revealed that although university students care about effective and eloquent speaking, they are not interested in printed products or publications related to oral expression. At the same time, the majority of the students (72%) stated that they enjoyed discussions about oral expression. This showed that university students like to share their ideas and exchange ideas. According to the opinions of Başaran and Erdem (2009) about pre-service teachers' eloquence; They think that getting a university education affects the speaking skill positively, but the oral expression course given at the university is insufficient for the development of this skill. All of the pre-service teachers have positive attitudes towards eloquence and there was no effect of class and department variables on these attitudes.

Some foreign studies have been done on speech anxiety; In the study conducted by Johnson (2012) and Loundmon (1992), gender and self-esteem were determined as important variables affecting students' speech anxiety levels. In the study conducted by Higgins (2001) it was determined that anxiety is at a high level in higher education.

As a result; It has been observed that the education given in the human relations and communication course has a significant effect on improving the speaking skills of physical education and sports teacher candidates. Observing the performances of the students and giving feedback on these performances during a course period is important for the continuation of learning. In the constructivist education system, determining the course status of the students is a task beyond grading their performance and aims to help the student see his/her strengths and weaknesses. The characteristics that develop in students can be listed as follows: Appropriate use of words, command of the subject, correct grammar, use of body language and gestures, speaking clearly and clearly, using language-style that will not disturb, enriching conversations with examples, using proverbs and idioms.

Practical courses on oral expression should be given more place in the curriculum of university students. Oral practices should be increased in human relations and communication, effective communication skills courses rather than theoretical weighting. In modern education systems, detailed studies should be carried out in order to use the language carefully and correctly.

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